

Accurate Measurements of Methane, Carbon Dioxide for Arctic and Wetland Conditions using NDIR Technology and AI-based Calibration

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Abstract—In this research, as a first step towards monitoring ambient green house gases (GHGs) in the Arctic and wetland regions, as targeted in the MISO EU project [1], we investigate the performance of new multi-channel NDIR gas sensor prototype working under harsh conditions, similar to these environments in the Lab framework, focusing on the influence of environmental conditions such as temperature (T) and humidity (H) on its measurement accuracy for carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) concentrations. Traditional calibration methods struggle to correct these environmental impacts effectively. To address this, we employ advanced machine learning and AI techniques, including Linear Regression, Support Vector Regression, Extreme Gradient Boosting, Neural Networks, and Gated recurrent units, to develop and refine calibration models.

Our findings demonstrate that AI-based models can significantly enhance the accuracy of NDIR sensors. The CO₂ calibration model using Neural Networks achieved an exceptionally high R₂ score of 0.9998, effectively mitigating the effects of temperature variations within a range of 40 °C to -20 °C. For CH₄ calibration, the Neural Network and GRU models performed admirably, achieving R₂ scores of 0.9903 and 0.9966, respectively, and successfully compensating for the impact of temperature and humidity.

Index Terms—NDIR, K96 sensor, Green House Gases, CO₂, CH₄, AI-based calibration, Deep learning, Neuron Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognized that achieving substantial reductions in the atmospheric concentrations of key greenhouse gases (GHGs), including carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), is an urgent priority [2]. However, significant uncertainties remain regarding the natural variability and climate-driven changes in emissions of these gases, particularly from major natural sources such as Arctic regions and wetlands. Without understanding how CO₂ and CH₄ sources have changed (and are changing) over time, and how these sources respond to climate warming, will be difficult or impossible to design effective mitigation and adaptation strategies.

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Monitoring GHGs in remote areas such as the Arctic and wetlands poses significant challenges in performing regular maintenance, and monitoring systems in these locations must operate with minimal power consumption, further complicating their design and deployment. High-end instrumentation used in reference observatories for GHG monitoring, such as Picarro and Los Gatos Research, are unsuitable for wide deployment in the areas due to their high cost of installation, regular maintenance and high power consumption.

Low-cost technologies could be adopted to increase both spatial and temporal resolution of environmental GHGs, especially in remote areas. Currently, low-cost sensor technologies are not yet ready for widely use in environmental monitoring, and are primarily designed for indoor and industrial applications where conditions are controlled and lower accuracy is sufficient. Thus, there is a need for i) affordable low-cost sensors with improved sensitivity, ii) low power consumption, iii) improving post-calibration data correction algorithms for enabling long-term monitoring. In the frame of environmental monitoring of gaseous air pollutants, photonic sensors are considered a technology suitable for harsh conditions such as the Arctics and wetlands [3]. One well-established photonic sensing technology is Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR) sensing, which has been developed and refined over decades [4]. However, today there are no commercially available low-cost NDIR sensors capable of CH₄ detection at background concentration levels (2 ppm), due to low sensitivity mainly caused by the short optical path length.

To address such limitations a novel NDIR sensor prototype, designed specifically for GHGs monitoring, is being developed by Senseair, a Swedish sensor manufacturing company, and a Project Partner in the EU-funded project MISO [1]. The Senseair K96 sensor, as shown in Fig. 1, is capable of simultaneous detection of CH₄, CO₂ and H₂O. In the K96 optical cell, mirrors are used to split the IR light into three channels, called SPL (short path length), MPL (medium path length) and LPL (long path length), and are calibrated to achieve a

Fig. 1. a) Unreleased NDIR sensors - K96 sensor from Senseair, combination of three gas measurements: CO₂, H₂O and CH₄. b) Absorption spectrum of CO₂, H₂O and CH₄. This figure shows the overlapping spectrum of H₂O and CH₄. c) Sensor structure demonstration

specific optical path length: 24 cm, 36 cm and 48 cm, with the aim to determine the concentration of CO₂, H₂O and CH₄. Laboratory studies showed that it can detect CH₄ at ppm-level accuracy [5]. This sensor is being demonstrated to be a valuable option for environmental monitoring applications.

The challenge of NDIR sensor is the effects of environmental conditions. Changing of IR source's temperature can cause a shift in the gas absorption spectrum [4]. The intensity of the IR light source, the photon detector response, and even the physical dimensions of the sensor's components can vary with temperature fluctuations. The latter can lead to a change in the optical path length within the sensor. These factors can significantly influence the accuracy and reliability of NDIR sensor measurements.

Secondly, the relation between water vapor and methane measurements poses significant challenges. This is primarily due to the fact that the water vapor (H₂O) has broadband absorption in a wide range of IR wavelengths, from 2.7 μm to 3.5 μm [6]. This band overlaps with the Methane (CH₄) absorption band as shown in Fig. 1b [7] where CH₄ wavelength band (around 3.375 μm) is within H₂O wavelength band. Thus, the presence of water interferes with the methane measurements, leading to high error of methane concentration. Thirdly, the optical path length of low-cost NDIR sensors is very short, e.g., 48 cm of the K96 sensor, compared to kilometers of picarro, making the sensitivity of methane measurement low.

Currently, thermal stabilization is used to control temperature of the sampled gas. However, this is inadequate for sustainable monitoring in hard-to-reach areas due to high power consumption [4]. Moreover, controlling the effect of water vapor on the measurements in wetlands is challenging since

the humidity is typically very high and varies dramatically.

To address these challenges, there is a critical need for an accurate and comprehensive model to compensate for changes in both humidity and temperature without relying on thermal stabilization. Such a model would improve the reliability and accuracy of low-cost NDIR sensors in diverse and challenging environmental conditions. By deploying this model at the device level, energy consumption for environmental control can be reduced, facilitating the deployment of more sensors in harsh environments.

Although Machine Learning and Deep Learning AI are powerful tools for solving complex mathematical models, AI-based calibration models for NDIR sensors are lacking for CH₄. Because with low cost NDIR sensor, the optical path length is short, leading to lack of adequate precision and accuracy for low concentration around 2 ppm, [8] used neural network to calibrate three natural gases which include CH₄ using array NDIR sensor. However the detective range is big, up to percent, equivalent to parts per hundred. In contrast, our application is 2 to 20 parts per million.

Alternatively, there are several AI-based CO₂ calibration models for NDIR sensors. [9] uses AI-based calibration methods to calibrate CO₂ concentrations from NDIR sensor. The testing conditions for temperature are from 0 °C to 45 °C, CO₂ concentration are from 400 ppm to 4000 ppm. Their analysis uses BP Neuron network, LSTM neuron network and GRU, achieving the highest R score of 91.542%. [10] calibrates the CO₂ concentration of a commercial NDIR sensor (Senseair NDIR SCD30, ELT S-100/300) using machine learning (ML). Temperature in these tests range from 7.1 to 37.8 °C, relative humidity from 14 to 79%. The ML models used in the paper are Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Linear Regression (LR), Multiple LR (MLR), and Linear Fractional Regression (LFR).

The open research questions are whether AI-based approaches can enhance the applicability of NDIR K96 sensors in Arctic and wetland environments for monitoring CH₄ and CO₂ concentrations and, if so, how effective are these methods in achieving accurate and reliable measurements under varying temperature and humidity conditions. To address these research questions, this paper presents a framework to develop AI-based CH₄ and CO₂ calibration models tackling the existing issues associated with low-cost NDIR K96 sensors. The contributions of this paper are:

- Developing and implementing a novel framework to develop AI-based CH₄ and CO₂ calibration models for low-cost NDIR sensors (Section III-A).
- Using the new framework to identify essential features for training these models, addressing a broad range of T (-20 to 40 °C) and RH (0-80 %) for CO₂, and low concentration (2-20 ppm) for ambient CH₄ with varied conditions (T: 0 to 32 °C; RH: 0-80 %) (Section III-B)).
- Comprehensive experimental evaluation of AI-based approaches (section III-C), which are used for CO₂ calibration, to investigate whether they are applicable for CH₄ calibration. Our results show that the Neural Network and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) approaches to CH₄ calibra-

tion perform exceptionally well, achieving R2 scores of 0.9903 and 0.9966, respectively (Section IV).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the state-of-the-art and related work. Section III presents the framework for developing AI-based CH_4 calibration models. Section IV presents the results of AI-based calibration models. Finally, Section V summarizes the achievements of this method and identifies any remaining gaps or areas for improvement.

II. RELATED WORK TO MITIGATE THE EFFECTS OF T&H ON MEASUREMENTS OF NDIR GAS SENSORS

For temperature effects, the mitigation methods focus on thermal stabilization. This involves maintaining a consistent temperature (T) to ensure that the output signal remains stable despite external temperature fluctuations.

For water vapor interference, developers from Senseair use MPL channel to observe spectra signal at $2.7 \mu\text{m}$ where only H_2O has absorption. Then, a calibration procedure was developed, which matches the absorbed light energy in LPL and MPL channels [11]. While testing is underway, a thermal stabilization is used to eliminate the effect of temperature on the sensor. The calibration range of H_2O concentration is from 50 ppm to 13200 ppm, equivalent to 0.2 % to 44 % in RH. Even though this method reduces a high amount of water interference, the error is still high for gas ambient monitoring, from 5 to 10 ppm, while the CH_4 concentration in the air is 2 ppm.

Difficulties when applying in harsh conditions: *Firstly*, as discussed, most methods used to mitigate the effects of T on NDIR sensors involve thermal stabilization. Additionally, it is recommended that NDIR sensors be operated at high T for optimal performance [4]. However, when deploying in the Arctic, maintaining a high T for the sensing unit consumes a significant amount of energy. This makes long-term applications unsustainable due to the high cost of continuous human intervention and energy demands. *Secondly* at wetland areas, the humidity is typically very high and varies dramatically. This makes it even more challenging to control the effect of water vapor on the measurements.

III. NOVEL FRAMEWORK TO CALIBRATE IR GAS SENSORS USING AI-BASED CALIBRATION MODELS

A. Environmental chamber and data collection.

At NILU, an environment chamber has been developed where temperature and humidity are controlled to simulate various weather conditions. This allows us to test sensor performance under different weather scenarios. Fig. 2a illustrates the chamber setup. Inside the environment chamber, Fig. 2b, an adjustable-temperature coil enables temperature changes from $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ or higher. The target gas (either CO_2 or CH_4), dry air, and humid air are mixed in the mixing chamber. By controlling the flow rate of each input air, the concentration of the target gas and humidity can be regulated. The mixed gas is then pumped into the sample chamber, where the Data acquisition electronic PCBs are placed for sampling

Fig. 2. a) Environment Chamber demonstration. b) Practical set up of Environment Chamber.

measurement. After being measured by the sensors, the gas is directly pumped to the Picarro 2401, used as a reference point for validating sensor performance. To evaluate the performance of the K96 module, five K96 modules are placed into the sensor chamber, allowing all to be tested simultaneously. The data from Data acquisition PCB and reference data from the Picarro are synchronized by matching timestamps. All five sensor measurements show similar patterns and results, and as such, one sensor is used as an example in this paper.

B. Lab experiment-based dataset.

CH_4 calibration dataset: To develop a robust calibration model for CH_4 concentrations, it is essential to account for both temperature and humidity influences. Fig. 3 illustrates the calibration dataset for CH_4 concentration. To across varying environmental conditions, the temperature varies from $32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At each temperature step, humidity is adjusted from 0 % to 80 %. Concurrently, at each humidity step, CH_4 concentration varies from 2 ppm to 25 ppm.

As shown in Fig. 3b, the baseline of CH_4 measurement is changed when the temperature and humidity vary. The influence of humidity and temperature significantly exceeds the sensitivity of the LPL signal to CH_4 concentration, making the calibration process more challenging.

CO_2 calibration dataset: Similar to CH_4 concentration, the temperature varies from $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in seven steps. At each temperature step, the CO_2 concentration is adjusted from 400 ppm to 6000 ppm, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Calibration dataset for CH_4 concentration. a) temperature and humidity conditions over time. b) CH_4 concentration condition and LPL signal over time. All the parameters are obtained simultaneously in the sensor chamber. The dashed orange and blue lines indicate the effect of temperature and humidity on the measurements.

Fig. 4. Calibration Dataset for CO_2 concentration. a) temperature and CH_4 concentration conditions over time. b) SPL signal over time. All signals are obtained simultaneously in the sensor chamber. The dashed orange lines indicate the effect of temperature on the measurements.

C. AI-based calibration method

In this paper, we employed seminal machine learning (ML) algorithms to develop the calibration model, including Linear Regression (LR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Neural Network (NN), and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). Following the development of these models, we analyzed and compared their performances. TABLE I presents the tested AI-based calibration models.

The NN models used for calibration for both CO_2 and CH_4 consist of five fully connected layers with 64 neurons each. CH_4 calibration model utilizes the LPL signal, temperature T, and humidity H as inputs. The calibration model for CO_2 concentration uses the SPL signal, SPL^2 , T and T^2 as inputs. An interesting observation during the training process for CO_2

TABLE I
AI-BASED CALIBRATION MODELS WHERE T AND H STAND FOR TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY, RESPECTIVELY. THE HYPER-PARAMETERS GIVE THE BEST RESULT IN OUR EXPERIMENTS.

Gas	Algorithm	Input Features	Hyper parameters
CH_4	LR	LPL, T, H	Degree=4
CH_4	SVR	LPL, T, H	
CH_4	XGBoost	LPL, T, H	$n_{\text{estimator}}=100000$
CH_4	NN	LPL, T, H	layer=5, width=64
CH_4	GRU	LPL, T, H	sequence=50, layer=2, hidden_size=64
CO_2	LR	SPL, T	Degree=4
CO_2	SVR	SPL, T	
CO_2	XGBoost	SPL, T	$n_{\text{estimator}}=100000$
CO_2	NN	SPL, SPL^2 , T, T^2	layer=5, width=64
CO_2	GRU	SPL, T	sequence=5, layer=2, hidden_size=32

Fig. 5. Temperature Compensation results using NN model. a) calibrated signal and temperature. b) LPL signal and temperature. The dashed line indicates the baseline shift of the LPL signal due to changes in temperature.

calibration models using NN was that incorporating additional input features, such as SPL^2 and T^2 , significantly enhanced the performance of the models. All input signals are normalized to a range between -1 and 1 before training to avoid dominance of features and get faster convergence. To ensure robust model development, 70 % of the dataset is used for training and the remaining 30 % is for testing.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. CH_4 calibration model

Temperature compensation: Fig. 5 shows the impact of temperature changes on both the LPL signal and the calibrated CH_4 concentration using the NN model. Unlike the LPL signal, the calibrated CH_4 concentration shows minimal sensitivity to temperature variations. The dashed line in Fig. 5b indicates the baseline shift of the LPL signal due to temperature changes. However, Fig. 5a demonstrates that the calibrated signal is barely affected, indicating effective temperature compensation by the NN model.

Water vapor/Humidity compensation: Fig. 6 illustrates the effect of humidity changes on the LPL signal and the calibrated CH_4 concentration using the NN model. Unlike the LPL signal, the calibrated CH_4 concentration shows minimal response to humidity variations. The dashed line in Fig. 6b

Fig. 6. Water Compensation results using NN model. a) Calibrated signal and humidity (H). b) LPL signal and H. The dashed line indicates the baseline shift of the LPL signal due to changes in H. A zoom-in is shown in Fig. 7.

TABLE II
AI-BASED CALIBRATION MODEL RESULTS FOR CH₄ CONCENTRATION
AFTER TRAINING ON TEST DATASET

Model	CH ₄		CO ₂	
	R2 Score	MSE	R2 Score	MSE
LR	0.8069	11.3653	0.9997	1007.1351
SVR	0.2334	45.1165	0.9985	4709.1311
XGBoost	0.9830	1.00187	0.9997	975.84
NN	0.9903	0.58	0.9998	600
GRU	0.9966	0.21	0.9997	1123

represents the LPL signal’s baseline shift due to humidity changes. However, the calibrated signal in Fig. 6a remains stable, indicating effective humidity compensation. While the NN model improves calibration significantly, there are instances where the calibrated signal does not perfectly match the reference signal, as illustrated in Fig. 7a. Initial high errors and spikes in the calibrated signal, not present in the reference signal, occur during sudden humidity changes.

Before calibration, the LPL signal and reference CH₄ concentration showed a poor match, with an initial R2 score of -1.2129 and a Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 130.266.

Overall performance analysis of all models: Table II summarizes the performance of various AI-based calibration models for estimating CH₄ concentration, evaluated by R2 Score and MSE. The **LR model** showed moderate performance with an R2 of 0.8069 but a relatively high MSE of 11.3653, suggesting less accurate predictions. The **SVR model** performed poorly, with an R2 of 0.2334 and a high MSE of 45.1165, indicating limited accuracy. The **XGBoost model** demonstrated excellent performance with an R2 of 0.9830 and an MSE of 1.00187, but its resolution is limited by the `n_estimators` parameter. The **NN model** had a strong performance among all tested models, achieving an R2 of 0.9903 and MSE of 0.58, indicating highly accurate predictions. The **GRU model** achieved the highest R2 of 0.9966 and an MSE of 0.2, signifying extremely accurate predictions. However, there is a higher risk of overfitting with the GRU model, as it can memorize specific patterns in the training data that may not represent real-world scenarios, making it potentially

Fig. 7. a) NN model: Spikes in the calibrated signals. b) GRU model: no spikes in calibrated signal

less effective when dealing with variable and random data in practical environments. This is particularly relevant given the higher number of parameters in GRU models (38273) compared to NN models (12801), which may make it less effective when coping with variable and random data in practical environments.

Hysteresis in Sensor Measurements: The spikes in NN model result can be explained by hysteresis in sensor measurements. There are differences in sensor readings when humidity is increasing or decreasing. This hysteresis effect is more pronounced in laboratory experiments, where the humidity change is more abrupt compared to the gradual changes typically observed in a real environment. Moreover, the NN model currently uses only one measurement as input and does not effectively learn the sequential changes in the signal. Consequently, the model encounters higher errors during periods of significant humidity changes. However, with the GRU model, these spikes are absent in the calibrated signal, as shown in Fig. 7b. The GRU model can remember past states of the signal, allowing it to learn and compensate for the hysteresis problem effectively. This results in more accurate predictions during periods of significant humidity changes.

B. CO₂ Calibration model

Table II presents the performance metrics of the AI-based calibration models for CO₂ concentration after training, evaluated on a test dataset. **NN:** achieves the highest R2 score of 0.9998, indicating it explains almost all the variance in the CO₂ concentration data. **LR, XGBoost and GRU:** all these three models perform exceptionally well with R2 scores of 0.9997. LR is preferred for its simplicity and interpretability in device-level deployment. Additionally, XGBoost’s performance can be constrained by the number of estimators (`n_estimators`). **SVR:** while still performing well, has a slightly lower R2 score of 0.9985 compared to the other models. **Error analysis:** Fig. 8b shows that the error of the calibrated signal

Fig. 8. a) Result of NN calibration model after training. The orange graph represents the predicted value (calibrated measurement), while the blue graph represents the reference value of the measurement. The green line shows the temperature condition. It is barely seen the affect of temperature on calibrated signal. b) Error of the calibration model. A zoom-in is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Calibrated CO₂ signal using NN model while the temperature changing from 2 °C to -3 °C

is relatively small. The reading error is less than 5% overall, compared to the reference signal's precision of 50 ppb.

All models demonstrate strong performance. There are **two main reasons for the high accuracy of the calibration model**. First, the **calibration range** of CO₂ concentration (from 400 ppm to 6000 ppm) is much higher than CH₄ concentration (from 2 ppm to 25 ppm). Second, **Insensitivity to Humidity**: SPL signal is not affected by humidity, thus the calibration model can learn greatly from the influence of temperature only.

Temperature compensation result: Fig. 8a shows that the temperature effect is nearly eliminated. Specifically, as temperature varies from 2°C to -3°C (Fig. 9), the calibrated CO₂ signal remains stable.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, with the framework that has been developed, the research has demonstrated significant advancements in the calibration and optimization of low-cost NDIR sensors using machine learning and AI techniques. Various AI-based models, including LR, SVR, XGBoost, NN, and GRU, are employed and analyzed, successfully enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the K96 sensors. By using environmental conditions as input features, the models were able to compensate for the effects caused by temperature and humidity on CO₂ and CH₄ concentration measurements.

The CO₂ calibration model using Neural Networks achieved an exceptionally high R2 score of 0.9998 compared to the

reference signal. This effectively eliminated the impact of temperature fluctuations within the range of 40 °C to -20 °C.

Two of the best models for CH₄ calibration were the Neural Network and GRU models, which performed exceptionally well, achieving R2 scores of 0.9903 and 0.9966, respectively. These models significantly compensated for the effects of temperature and humidity on CH₄ concentration measurements.

Despite these high R2 scores, certain limitations need to be addressed, particularly the issues of hysteresis for the Neural Network model and overfitting. To overcome these challenges, more robust models should be applied which can resolve issues such as hysteresis and improve generalization.

VI. FUTURE WORKS

While this research has significantly improved the accuracy and reliability of low-cost NDIR sensors, several future steps could further enhance their utility and performance:

Firstly, more **advanced AI algorithms** such as hybrid models that combine different types of neural networks should be explored for even more accurate calibration by addressing issues like hysteresis and overfitting. Due to manufacturing, each sensor will have different scaling calibration factor, **transfer learning techniques** are needed to adapt the calibration models for use with different sensors. Transfer learning can also apply to different types of NDIR sensors or other gas sensing technologies. **Conduct more metrological evaluation and extensive field experiments** in various environmental conditions to validate the selectivity, repeatability, reproducibility, robustness and reliability of the calibration model.

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